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PROPOSING EFFICIENT WAYS TO PLAN THE USAGE OF TRAIN LOCOMOTIVES

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Annotation: The main factor influencing the choice of a rational type of train locomotives is the consumption of fuel and energy resources. At the same time, the parameters of cars and transported goods have a significant impact on the value of consumed fuel and energy resources on train traction. The article proposes innovative ways of using locomotives and the way of planning. Based on this distinctive analysis and tables are proposed.

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Key words: locomotives, operation, railway sections, scientific work, train

1. Introduction

The operation of train locomotives is a complex scientific and technical issue with many steps. Therefore, today there are a number of scientific works aimed at solving this issue [1-11]. In all existing scientific work, train locomotives ' maintenance fleet is determined on the basis of analytical and graphoanalytical methods, and the second of them is the most significant [12]. Graphoanalytically, the calculation of the need for a fleet of locomotives in operation is determined based on the data of the graph of the movement of trains. However, in the existing scientific work, the train action graph does not describe how the Times of arrival and departure of freight trains to and from stations are determined, and is based on the condition that the "locomotive waits for content" of the attachment of locomotives to trains.

2. DEVELOPMENT OF AN INNOVATIVE METHOD OF EFFECTIVE PLANNING FOR THE USE OF TRAIN LOCOMOTIVES

It is known that in order to minimize the waiting times of train locomotives at turning points on railway sections, it is necessary that the arrival and departure times at the station are taken into account in the graph. In general, the maximum and minimum amounts of the standing of train locomotives and contents at turning points (respectively $t_{max(lok)}$, $t_{max(tar)}$, $t_{min(lok)}$, $t_{min(tar)}$) are calculated as in the Figure 1.

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Since a variable graph is used, any train ready for departure will have to wait for the release of the train (t_k) the value of (t_k) is determined depending on the technical equipment of the railway section and the parameters of the train flows.

Picture 1. Schematic display of the maximum and minimum amounts of standing at turning points of train locomotives and compositions

As can be seen from Figure 1, the minimum number of train locomotive stays at Turn points corresponds to the "line waits for locomotive" condition of attachment of locomotives to trains, and the minimum number of linings stays corresponds to the "line waits" condition. In the train traffic graph, the Times of arrival and departure of freight trains to and from stations are interrelated, and the maximum stay Times of their locomotives at the turnpikes where N_l ta train traffic is available can be determined as follows:

$$t_{\max(lok)} = \frac{12}{\sum N_l} + t_k \quad ,$$

(1)

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As you know, in the conditions of railway sections equipped with modern information and control systems, there is an opportunity to plan train work for the next day. As a result, we will be able to determine the departure and arrival times of freight trains from the stations at each turn and exchange points for the day when train work is planned. Table 1 presents the results of determining departure-arrival times at the turning point, where the flow of freight trains is 18.

T/p	Of the pair train number	Of the pair train date of arrival	Of the pair train departure time	Of the odd train number	Of the odd train departure date	Of the odd train departure time
1	2034	01.05.2023	20:24:00	2033	02.05.2023	20:18:00
2	2036	18.07.2022	22:22:00	2035	18.07.2022	23:04:00
3	2002	18.07.2022	00:12:00	2001	18.07.2022	0:48:00
4	2004	18.07.2022	00:48:00	2003	18.07.2022	1:27:00
5	2006	18.07.2022	01:19:00	2005	18.07.2022	2:39:00
6	2008	18.07.2022	03:38:00	2007	18.07.2022	3:07:00
7	2010	18.07.2022	04:39:00	2009	18.07.2022	3:41:00
8	2012	18.07.2022	06:15:00	2011	18.07.2022	4:09:00

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9	2014	18.07.2022	06:28:00	2013	18.07.2022	6:25:00
10	2016	18.07.2022	07:47:00	2015	18.07.2022	6:43:00
11	2018	18.07.2022	08:57:00	2017	18.07.2022	7:11:00
12	2020	18.07.2022	10:07:00	2019	18.07.2022	8:06:00
13	2022	18.07.2022	13:11:00	2021	18.07.2022	9:46:00
14	2024	18.07.2022	15:42:00	2023	18.07.2022	11:14:00
15	2026	18.07.2022	16:31:00	2025	18.07.2022	14:14:00
16	2028	18.07.2022	18:10:00	2027	18.07.2022	14:48:00
17	2030	18.07.2022	18:31:00	2029	18.07.2022	17:34:00
18	2032	18.07.2022	18:53:00	2031	18.07.2022	18:35:00

Table 1. Departure-arrival times of freight trains at the turning point

Based on the data of Table 1, possible connections of train locomotives are made at the turntable. To determine the periods of stay at the turning points of train locomotives and compositions, we will develop an advanced method of planning the efficient use of train locomotives based on the number of traction units that are shay to work. In this we set the time of arrival of trains to Station 1 and the time of departure t_i^l from it T_j^l , here $i = \overline{1, N_1}$; $j = \overline{1, N_1}$.

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Schedules of freight trains departing from the station and arriving at it (schedules 1-2) rotation station splits the time axis k into pieces. In doing so, the number of contents increases after each train arrives at the station, $\min k_v = 0$ and decreases from $1 \leq v \leq 2N_l + 1$. To per unit after each train departs. Otherwise at least one content will remain standing at the rotation station for a day, and this, in turn, will allow you to determine all κ_v .

For a state equal to the number of contents, let's put the κ_v pieces in the contents that are at the rotation station at intervals. In this case t_i^l , the receiving table t_j^l may be linked to the dispatch table without increasing the number of locomotives, when the indices $k_v > 0$ are equal to for all $[t_i^l; T_j^l]$ the pieces that apply to it. Otherwise, the connection of these tables will lead to an increase in the total number of locomotives. For example, t_1^l a schedule can be linked to T_1^l and T_2^l , cannot be linked to t_1^l and T_3^l , as such a connection will result in an increase in the required number of locomotives.

Table 2 provides an example of a matrix of possible connections of locomotives.

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T_j^l		T_1^l	T_2^l	T_3^l	T_4^l	T_5^l	T_6^l
t_i^l							
t_1^l							
t_2^l							
t_3^l							
t_4^l							
t_5^l							
t_6^l							

Table 2. An example of a matrix of possible connections of locomotives

$\{x_{ij}^l\}$ we introduce the matrix of links:

$\{x_{ij}^l\} = 1$, if the arrival schedule is linked to the departure schedule;

(2)

0 – without the opposite.

Where each arrival table t_i^l can be associated with no more than one dispatch table T_j^l , and vice versa each T_j^l can be associated with no more than one t_i^l , the following inequality holds:

$$\sum_i x_{ij}^l \leq 1, \forall_j; \sum_j x_{ij}^l \leq 1, \forall_i$$

(3)

That is, there is no more than one unit in each row of matrix of links (Figure 2).

Picture 2. Image of possible connections of train locomotives at the turntable

We draw up a rotation graph of train locomotives according to the times of the traffic graph given for a railway plot with a number of stations of two, which we take as . $l = 1, 2$ we define the indices k_v relative to the time-axis slices.

$$\{x_{ij}^l\} =$$

T_j^l	T_1^l	T_2^l	T_3^l	T_4^l	T_5^l	T_6^l	T_7^l	T_8^l	T_9^l	T_{10}^l
t_1^l	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
t_2^l	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1	1

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t_3^l	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1
t_4^l	1	1	1	1	0	1	1	1	1	1
t_5^l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1	1
t_6^l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0	1
t_7^l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	0
t_8^l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
t_9^l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1
t_{10}^l	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1	1

Table 3. The matrix of links for the first rotation station

For each of the matrices in Table 3 and 4, the "contents await the locomotive"

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condition is followed by the attachment of the locomotives to the trains (Table 5), and this attachment continues until the "locomotive waits for the contents" condition (Table 6).

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1	2034	01.05.2023	20:24:00	2033	02.05.2023	20:18:00
2	2036	01.05.2023	22:22:00	2035	02.05.2023	23:04:00
3	2002	01.05.2023	00:12:00	2001	02.05.2023	0:48:00
4	2004	01.05.2023	00:48:00	2003	02.05.2023	1:27:00
5	2006	01.05.2023	01:19:00	2005	02.05.2023	2:39:00
6	2008	01.05.2023	03:38:00	2007	02.05.2023	3:07:00
7	2010	01.05.2023	04:39:00	2009	02.05.2023	3:41:00
8	2012	01.05.2023	06:15:00	2011	02.05.2023	4:09:00
9	2014	01.05.2023	06:28:00	2013	02.05.2023	6:25:00
10	2016	01.05.2023	07:47:00	2015	02.05.2023	6:43:00

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11	2018	01.05.2023	08:57:00	2017	02.05.2023	7:11:00
12	2020	01.05.2023	10:07:00	2019	02.05.2023	8:06:00
13	2022	01.05.2023	13:11:00	2021	02.05.2023	9:46:00
14	2024	01.05.2023	15:42:00	2023	02.05.2023	11:14:00
15	2026	01.05.2023	16:31:00	2025	02.05.2023	14:14:00
16	2028	01.05.2023	18:10:00	2027	02.05.2023	14:48:00
17	2030	01.05.2023	18:31:00	2029	02.05.2023	17:34:00
18	2032	01.05.2023	18:53:00	2031	02.05.2023	18:35:00

Table 5. Results of attaching locomotives to trains under the condition that "the line waits for the locomotive" at the turntable

T/p	Of the pair train number	Of the pair train date of arrival	Of the pair train departure time	Of the odd train number	Of the odd train departure date	Of the odd train departure time
1	2034	01.05.2023	20:24:00	2003	02.05.2023	1:27:00
2	2036	01.05.2023	22:22:00	2005	02.05.2023	2:39:00

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3	2002	01.05.2023	00:12:00	2007	02.05.2023	3:07:00
4	2004	01.05.2023	00:48:00	2009	02.05.2023	3:41:00
5	2006	01.05.2023	01:19:00	2011	02.05.2023	4:09:00
6	2008	01.05.2023	03:38:00	2013	02.05.2023	6:25:00
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13	2022	01.05.2023	13:11:00	2027	02.05.2023	14:48:00
14	2024	01.05.2023	15:42:00	2029	02.05.2023	17:34:00
15	2026	01.05.2023	16:31:00	2031	02.05.2023	18:35:00
16	2028	01.05.2023	18:10:00	2033	02.05.2023	20:18:00
17	2030	01.05.2023	18:31:00	2035	02.05.2023	23:04:00
18	2032	01.05.2023	18:53:00	2001	02.05.2023	0:48:00

Table 6. Results of attaching locomotives to trains on the condition that the "locomotive waits for content" at the turntable

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Under the conditions of a graph of the movement of unpaired trains, data on train locomotives nominated for reserve shipment [1] can be obtained using programs developed within the study.

3. Conclusion

1. It has been found that the accumulation processes of load train compositions are subject to the Erlang distribution law, which has different distribution parameters. As a result, it was possible to determine the departure times of freight trains from train-building stations and, based on these times, the time for each freight train to arrive at the next technical station.

2. A method was developed to determine the average stay Times of train locomotives and lineups within the limits of the traction shoulders for the R Ta option, from the "line waits for locomotive" condition to the "line waits for Line" condition. As a result, it has been proven that the fleet of locomotive use (in the studied case) varies by up to 16% in terms of options for attaching train locomotives from Condition 1 to Condition 2 to compositions. Therefore, the application of the conditions for attaching train locomotives to the formations, based on the number of train locomotives that were shay to work in the next day, will provide the basis for the effective operation of rolling stock.

3. A program has been created for the purpose of calculating the fleet of use of freight locomotives based on the graphical Times of trains. As a result, the

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innovation method of effective planning for the use of train locomotives was developed on the basis of minimizing the standing Times of the rolling stock at the limits of the traction shoulders.

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